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Research Article

**AMPC B-LACTAMASE PRODUCING BACTERIA INDUCED
NEONATAL SEPSIS AND ITS ASSOCIATION TO ANTIBIOTIC
MANAGEMENT AND EXCESSIVE USE OF INVASIVE
PROCEDURES**¹Dr. Maha Arshad, ²Dr. Insha_e_Qudrat Tirmizi, ³Dr Hina Nasir¹WMO DHQ Teaching Hospital Gujranwala²House Officer Mayo Hospital Lahore³Allied Hospital, Faisalabad.**Abstract:**

Objective: We aimed to determine the antimicrobial profile and occurrence of the AmpC β -lactamase which produces the bacteria.

Methods: Our research was carried out on 1914 blood samples of the all suspected cases of neonatal septicemia at Allied Hospital, Faisalabad in the timeframe of October 2016 to July 2017. Gram staining was used for the identification of the isolates and API 20E & NE tests were also processed. Screening of the negative gram isolates was carried out for bacteria producing AmpC β -lactamase against cefotaxime, ceftazidime and ceftiofur resistance, it was confirmed through base inhibition method.

Results: Gram-positive and negative bacteria cases were identified respectively as 54 gram-negative (8.49%) and 582 gram-positive (91.5%). In the negatively gram isolates, 141 AmpC producers (22%) were hundred percent resistant against ceftiofur, co-amoxiclav, cefotaxime, ceftazidime, cefixime, cefuroxime, cefpodoxime, ceftriaxone, amikacin, gentamicin and aztreonam. Low level of resistance was found against sulbactam cefoperazone, cefepime, ciprofloxacin, piperacillin-tazobactam & meropenem with respective proportions of 24.8%, 30.4%, 20.5%, 10.6% & 2.1%. Every isolate had sensitivity against imipenem. Because of various interventions patients were treated with AmpC β -lactamases where intravenous (IV) line was observed nasogastric tube, Ambu bag, endotracheal tube, ventilator & surgery having respective proportions of 37.6%, 8.5%, 3.5%, 2.1% & 0.7%.

Conclusion: Excessive utilization of the third generation cephalosporins and invasive procedures is to be marginalized and inhibited in order to avoid AmpC β -lactamases emergence in the children (neonates).

Keywords: Antimicrobial Resistance, AmpC β -lactamase, Multidrug-Resistant, Neonatal Sepsis and Bacteria.

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INTRODUCTION

β -lactamases are produced through numerous bacteria and it is a bacterial enzyme providing resistance against β -lactam antibiotics including carbapenems, penicillin, monobactams and cephalosporins. AmpC β -lactamases hydrolyze with a broader spectrum of cephalosporins which includes cefotaxime, ceftaxime, ceftazidime [1]. Presence of these enzymes can be found in gram-negative bacteria including *Escherichia coli*, *Salmonella* species, *Klebsiella* species, *Enterobacter* species, *Shigella*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Citrobacter* species, *Providencia*, *Serratia marcescens*, *Morganella morganii* and *Proteus mirabilis* [2].

The standard method for the detection is lacking to detect AmpC β -lactamases; whereas, numerous strategies are used for the screening of AmpC. AmpC detection is made through the three-dimensional test with the help of indicator drugs such as ceftazidime, ceftaxime or cefotaxime [3]. Inhibitor-Based Method is also used to detect AmpC β -lactamases which uses boronic acid as AmpC enzyme inhibitor [4].

Klebsiella pneumoniae, *Escherichia coli*, *Acinetobacter baumannii*, *Citrobacter diversus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Enterobacter cloacae*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Streptococcus pyogenes* were mostly involved in the bacteria that caused neonatal sepsis [5]. Higher resistance levels were developed because of the 3rd generation of the cephalosporins. The sulbactam, carbapenems and amikacin were also used for the management of neonatal sepsis that was caused because of the AmpC produced strains; whereas, in case of organism mutations they can also cause resistance to carbapenem [1]. For the inhibition of the AmpC β -lactamase, we can also utilize Boronic acid [4]. We can also avoid multidrug resistance through limited use of the 3rd generation of cephalosporins for neonatal sepsis [6].

Unjustified use of the 3rd generation cephalosporins, invasive procedures and prolonged stay in the hospital were a major factor of risk. We aimed to determine the antimicrobial profile and occurrence of the AmpC β -lactamase which produces the bacteria.

METHODS:

Our research was carried out on 1914 blood samples of the all suspected cases of neonatal septicemia at Allied Hospital, Faisalabad in the timeframe of October 2016 to July 2017. Gram staining was used for the identification of the isolates and API 20E & NE tests were also processed. Screening of the negative gram isolates was carried out for bacteria

producing AmpC β -lactamase against cefotaxime, ceftazidime and ceftaxime resistance, it was confirmed through base inhibition method. Blood samples were incubated at a temperature of 37°C. MacConkey agar plates were used for culturing after incubation of the blood samples. Identification of the bacteria was made through colony morphology, oxidase test, lactose fermentation, Gram's staining, API 20E & 20NE and biochemical tests [7]. Disc diffusion method was used for the screening of the isolates [8]. Isolates were resistant against cefotaxime, ceftazidime and ceftaxime which positive after screening for AmpC β -lactamases. Further confirmation was also made by using boronic acid through inhibition disc method. For this method, we used cefotaxime-clavulanate and ceftazidime-clavulanate by applying them on the agar plate. Detection of isolates was made as a producer of AmpC in case of a keyhole formation (synergism) in between boronic acid and (cephalosporin + clavulanate) [9].

Every bacterial stain was tested for sensitivity on 90 mm Muller Hinton agar plates. Strains were controlled through *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (ATCC-700603) and *E. coli* (ATCC-25922). Various antibiotics were used to test isolates which included aztreonam (30 μ g), amikacin (30 μ g), cefotaxime (30 μ g), cefixime (5 μ g), cefpodoxime (30 μ g), amoxicillin-clavulanate (20/10 μ g), ceftaxime (30 μ g), cefepime (30 μ g), meropenem (10 μ g), imipenem (10 μ g), ceftaxime (30 μ g), ceftazidime (30 μ g), sulbactam ceftazidime (75 / 30 μ g), gentamicin (10 μ g), ciprofloxacin (5 μ g), piperacillin-tazobactam (100 / 10 μ g) and cefuroxime (30 μ g). With the application of the mentioned antibiotics overnight incubation was made at 37°C. CLSI guidelines were used for the measurement of zonal diameter after incubation process [8]. We also reviewed the record of the patients. Various other investigations were also documented which included a nasogastric tube, intravenous line, endotracheal tube, Ambu bag, surgery and ventilator.

RESULTS:

Gram-positive and negative bacteria cases were identified respectively as 54 gram-negative (8.49%) and 582 gram-positive (91.5%). In the negatively gram isolates, 141 AmpC producers (22%) were hundred percent resistant against ceftaxime, ceftazidime, cefixime, cefuroxime, cefpodoxime, ceftaxime, amikacin, gentamicin and aztreonam. Low level of resistance was found against sulbactam ceftazidime, cefepime, ciprofloxacin, piperacillin-tazobactam & meropenem with respective proportions of 24.8%, 30.4%, 20.5%,

10.6% & 2.1%. Every isolate had sensitivity against imipenem. Because of various interventions patients were treated with AmpC β -lactamases where intravenous (I/V) line was observed nasogastric tube,

ambu bag, endotracheal tube, ventilator & surgery having respective proportions of 37.6%, 8.5%, 3.5%, 2.1% & 0.7% as reflected in Table – I.

Table – I: Distribution of AmpC β -lactamase producing bacteria isolated in neonatal sepsis (141).

Bacteria	Number	Percentage
Enterobacter cloacae	80	56.7
Enterobacter sakazakii	20	14.2
Escherichia coli	14	9.9
Citrobacter freundii	8	5.7
Klebsiella pneumoniae	8	5.7
Klebsiella oxytoca	4	2.8
Serratia marcescens	3	2.1
Acinetobacter baumannii	2	1.4
Pseudomonas aeruginosa	1	0.7
Aeromonas hydrophila	1	0.7

Table – II shows the resistance of 141 bacteria producing AmpC against ceftazidime, co-amoxiclav, cefuroxime, cefotaxime, ceftriaxone, cefixime and cefpodoxime. Various rates of resistance have been analyzed in the given tabular data.

Table – II: Antibiotic resistance of AmpC β -lactamase producing bacteria

Antibiotics	Resistant Number	Percentage
Co-amoxiclav	141	100
Ceftazidime	141	100
Ceftriaxone	141	100
Cefotaxime	141	100
Cefuroxime	141	100
Cefixime	141	100
Cefpodoxime	141	100
Cefoxitin	140	99.3
Gentamicin	136	96.4
Amikacin	132	93.6
Aztreonam	92	65.2
Cefepime	43	30.4
Sulbactam+cefoperazone	35	24.8
Ciprofloxacin	29	20.5
Piperacillin+tazobactam	15	10.6
Meropenem	3	2.1
Imipenem	0	0

Numerous invitational procedures were observed as 72 intravenous line (I/V) 51.1%, 53 nasogastric tubes 37.6%, 5 endotracheal tubes 3.5%, 12 Ambu bag 8.5%, 3 ventilators 2.1% and 1 Surgery 0.7% as shown in Table – III.

Table – III: Interventional Frequency among AmpC β -lactamase harbouring neonates

Interventions	Number	Percentage
Intravenous line	72	51.1
Nasogastric tube	53	37.6
Ambu bag	12	8.5
Endotracheal tube	5	3.5
ventilator	3	2.1
Surgery	1	0.7

DISCUSSION:

Mortality and morbidity are very much associated with the neonatal sepsis in Pakistani neonates. Gram-positive and negative bacteria cases were identified respectively as 54 gram-negative (8.49%) and 582 gram-positive (91.5%), these outcomes can be compared with other research studies where gram-negative was more than gram positive with the proportion of 92.8% to 7.2% respectively [10]. Another research reported gram negative and positive respectively 80.4% and 20.6% in neonatal sepsis [8]. Different outcomes have been reported by Muhammad *et al.* as they reported higher gram-negative bacteria frequency than gram positive bacteria with respective proportions of 54.6% to 45.4% [11]. Microbiologists face real challenge AmpC β -lactamases identification. Rate of bacteria production through AmpC β -lactamase was observed as 22.0% in this particular research; whereas, other studies reported as 26.8%, 19.61%, 20.7% and 35.5% [12 – 15].

Most prevalent AmpC producing isolates were *Enterobacter sakazakii* and *Enterobacter cloacae*. The emergence of the resistance is mostly linked with the *Enterobacter* species which is against cephalosporins than associated bacteria in case if treated with a broader spectrum of cephalosporins [1]. Gram-negative had a repeated nosocomial pathogen of *Enterobacter* species which caused 11% cases of pneumonia [16]. Every isolate produced by AmpC were resistant to ceftazidime, co-amoxiclav, cefuroxime, cefotaxime, ceftriaxone, cefixime and cefpodoxime. A research observed antimicrobial resistance establishment of AmpC producing pattern of Gram-negative bacteria to ceftazidime, gentamicin, amikacin, aztreonam, ceftazidime and sulbactam-cefoperazone having respective proportions of 99.3%, 96.4%, 93.6%, 65.2%, 30.4% & 24.8% [15]. The resistance of the AmpC β -lactamases was reported against aztreonam and ceftazidime [11, 14]. We did not observe a higher level of resistance of the

AmpC producers to sulbactam-cefoperazone and cefepime which is comparable with the outcomes of other same research studies [15, 17].

According to the outcomes of this particular research, ciprofloxacin resistance was 20.5% and numerous isolates had a sensitivity to various antibiotic as observed in another research such as sensitivity to ciprofloxacin was 30% [20]. Resistance to piperacillin-tazobactam was reported in our research as 10.6% that can be compared with another research which reported the same as 78% [18]. Resistance to meropenem was reported as 4.9% and no isolate was resistant against imipenem. It reflects the sensitivity of majority of isolates to carbapenems. Antibiotic susceptibility was studied by Beatrice and Herman about AmpC β -lactamase producing a pattern on carbapenems and Enterobacteriaceae as an effective antimicrobial medicine to treat AmpC producing Enterobacteria induced infection [19, 20].

AmpC β -lactamase producing bacteria was managed in numerous interventions such as nasogastric (NG) tube, an intravenous line (IV), an endotracheal tube (ETT), Ambu bag, surgery and ventilator support. Higher frequency was reported in 72 IV cases (51.1%). Authors also reported IV as risk factors linked with the nosocomial bacteremia and ambu bags as a cause of pathogenic transmission [21, 22]. Microbial colonization is also associated with the utilization of ETT which is a significant reason for the ventilator linked pneumonia [23]. Infection association was probed by an author which reported infection rate associated to a ventilator as (0.44 / 1000 days on a ventilator); whereas, central-line as (4.6 / 1000 days on a catheter) [24]. Pathogens can also be associated with various surgical procedures and contaminated apparatus. Bloodstream infections are also associated with sepsis and invasive procedures [25].

CONCLUSION:

AmpC β -lactamase producing bacteria induced neonatal sepsis causes mortality and treatment failure. Various epidemiological research studies are required to study the infection source during hospitalization. Excessive use of the invasive procedure is to be limited to reduce complications and unjustified broader spectrum cephalosporins are also to be restricted. Antibiotic utilization policy needs to be reviewed for the reduction of AmpC producing bacteria emergence. Excessive utilization of the third generation cephalosporins and invasive procedures is to be marginalized and inhibited in order to avoid AmpC β -lactamases emergence in the children (neonates).

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